

1 **HES6 and HEY1, along with DLL1 form a Notch transcriptional network in the trophectoderm.**

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7 We measured total transcription in the inner cell mass (ICM) and the trophectoderm (TE) of the human
8 embryo to understand the mechanisms underlying TE commitment. We describe here identification of
9 Hes6, Hey1 and Dll1 as a lineage commitment factor or lineage commitment cooperating factor in
10 embryonic stem cells of the human embryo.

11 Citations

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